

THE LAW RELATING TO INSIDER TRADING – THE INDIAN LANDSCAPE

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Abstract

In today's day, business is expanding in the global markets and with it there is considerable amount of growth in the financial markets- Bond market, share market, derivative market. With the increase in such trading, there has been a development in one particular form of trading -Insider Trading. 'Insider trading' in financial markets refers to trading in securities such as equity and bonds by company insiders who have access to exclusive information about the issuer of a particular security before such information is released to the general public. This allows insiders to benefit from buying or selling shares before they fluctuate in price. Investigations in these types of transactions have proved the involvement of the high ranking officers of the companies in the crime, sophisticatedly referred to as white-collar crime. Insider trading also disrupts the financial equilibrium in the capital market as it erodes public confidence in its functioning. The law governing insider trading generally aims to discipline the trade by barring shareholders who are in a dominant position on account of their access to non-public price-sensitive information from abusing it. Laws prohibiting insider trading animate the over-arching objective of corporate accountability and ensure higher standards in corporate conduct. Corporations have been looted by the insider traders, diversifying internal information to an external in lieu of cash. The transactions that are prohibited are the trading by an insider in breach of a duty of trust or confidence in the stock of a company based on non-public information to the exclusion of others. If such trading is allowed to go unchecked in capital markets, than all those individuals or persons who are holding the insider information will have an unfair advantage inselling or buying of the securities with such information and all those without the insider information will have a disadvantage and will be losers in the market. This will eventually lead to investors losing confidence in the stock market and they will desert the market, thereby eliminating and destroying important functions of the stock market such as capital formation. Insider trading has a negative or harmful impact on the growth and sustainability of the capital market more particularly the secondary market. The Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) is the statutory regulatory authority regulating the capital market in India. With the intention to overcome the inadequacies of the previous regulations, SEBI notified SEBI (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations 2015; to regulate Insider Trading replacing the earlier SEBI (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations 1992. The article analyses the legal framework for regulating transactions wherein a corporate insider trades on information before it is disclosed to the general public. The article seeks to examine the effectiveness of the 2015 SEBI (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations. The article also seeks to look into the laws regulating Insider trading in India. And make some suggestions to bring some changes to curb these loopholes in regulation.

Key words: Insider Trading, SEBI, Capital market, regulations

Introduction

There is a need for every household to inculcate savings habits in them, so that these savings can be mobilised into productive usage like manufacturing or using it for trade or commerce. Now this can be possible only if there is a financial system placed. For any economy to grow it must have in place a sound financial system which in turn will help in production and the overall growth of the economy.

The backbone of any financial system across the world is the capital market and more particularly the securities market, as we know that it aids in stimulating growth and investment by bringing together the corporates and the investors. The domestic investors or the foreign investors who have surplus money lying ideal with them, considers the stock market or the secondary market as the route to make an investment by buying the securities of the companies thereby facilitating the corporates to utilize the public money.

A financial system is an institutional arrangement through which financial surpluses are mobilised from the units generating surplus income and transferring them to the others in need of them. Every company has internal resources to raise funds and many a times it resorts to debt financing. These are the traditional ways whereby the companies raise funds for its projects, modernisation, expansion, diversification etc. We also notice that an increase in the performance of some companies and the amazing increase of their securities particularly the share prices boost the market opinion to divert the savings more and more into equity investments in companies.

The capital market is an important and efficient conduit to channel and mobilize funds to enterprises, both private and government. The securities market a constituent of the capital market is the market for those financial instruments that are commonly and readily transferable by sale. The two inter-dependent and inseparable segments of the Securities Market are the new issues (primary) market and the stock (secondary) market.

It is to be noted that the primary market provides the channel for sale of new securities, on the other hand the secondary market deals in securities previously issued. It is the primary market wherein resources are mobilised by companies through issue of new securities. It is through the primary market that funds flow for productive purposes from investors to the corporates. It would not be incorrect to say that the primary market creates and offers the merchandise for the secondary market. Secondary market essentially comprises of stock exchanges which provides a mechanism for buying and selling of securities by investors. All those, who hold securities the stock market allows and permit them to adjust their holdings in their assessment of risk and return. They can also sell securities for cash to meet their liquidity needs. The trading of securities is confined only to stock exchanges and these trading platforms of stock exchanges are accessible only through stock brokers.

Securities market

The security market is a market where the trading is done in terms of securities. It is just like any other market with the main function of buying and selling of securities. It refers to the markets for those financial instruments / securities that are commonly and readily transferable by sale. They are issued by either a company or the government. The Securities Market as we know has two inter-dependent and inseparable segments, the new issues (primary) market and the stock (secondary) market. Now the new securities are issued or we may say are sold for the first time in the primary market and later on they are traded in the secondary market or the stock exchange. Here the secondary market is providing a platform to the holders of the

securities to adjust their risk associated with those securities by trading with their securities where these securities can be sold or purchased.

As we know the secondary market is where the already issued securities are traded and the platform is known as the stock exchange. The trading of securities on the stock exchange is done through an Intermediary known as stock broker who is registered with SEBI. No person other than a stock broker can trade with the securities at the stock exchange and there is no place other than the stock exchange where trading of securities can take place.

The stock market provides for a platform where there is freedom to negotiate and decide on the price of the securities. It further provides free marketability of the securities. Therefore the stock exchange is also referred to as the nerve centre of the capital market, as it not only reflects the economic trend of the investor but also the dreams, aspirations hopes of the investors.

Savings are linked to investments by a variety of intermediaries through a range of complex financial products called 'securities' to include shares, scrips, stocks, bonds, debentures, debenture stock etc. There are a set of economic units who demand securities in lieu of funds and others who supply securities for funds.

These demand for and supply of securities and funds determine, under competitive market conditions in goods and securities market, the prices of securities. We know that these Securities are fungible and negotiable financial instruments.

Insider Trading

To understand it in an easy way is that insider trading is the trading of stocks or other securities of public companies by anyone who has an access to any non-public information about the company. To bring in more clarity, insider trading is a misconduct wherein company's securities are traded or undertaken by people who by the virtue of their work have access to the non-public information which can be crucial for making investment decisions. Insider trading is defined as 'the use of material non-public information in trading the shares of the company by a corporate insider or any other person who owes a fiduciary duty to the company'. To understand it better we can consider an example, say Mr Xavier is an employee of a company and having access to strategic information about the company and this person Mr X uses this information for trading in stock's or securities of the company, it is called insider trading. Therefore we can say that Insider trading is the theft of relevant & confidential information and abusing it for personal benefits.

Insider trading implies withholding of relevant information from the shareholders or releasing it at such intervals so as to fully exploit its insider potential. This form of siphoning of excess profits of the company by the insiders not only devalues the shares but also deprives rightful owners of their interest. Simply put, insider trading to investment markets is what matchfixing is to sports. Insider trading is nothing but the breach of the fiduciary relationship between the company and its investors. Therefore it is an activity which disrupts the financial equilibrium in the capital market as it erodes public confidence in its functioning.

A High-powered Committee constituted by the Government of India in 1987 defined insider trading as “the trading in the shares of a company by the person who is in the management of the company or are close to them on the basis of undisclosed price sensitive information regarding the working of the company, which they possess but which is not available to others”.

SEBI through its regulations clarifies who is an ‘insider’ and states that insider means any person who is either a connected person or is in possession of or having access to unpublished price sensitive information. Therefore, it would include persons connected on the basis of being in any contractual, fiduciary, or employment relationship that allows such person access to unpublished price-sensitive information.

As per the India companies Act insider trading means an act of subscribing, buying, selling, dealing, or agreeing to buy, sell or deal in any securities by any director or key managerial personnel or any other officer of a company either as principal or agent if he is reasonably expected to have access to any non-public price-sensitive information in respect of securities of a company. This section prohibits directors or key managerial personnel of a company from engaging in insider trading. This would imply that if the information which was used to trade in a particular share or security was not public then it would be considered insider trading. It should be understood that even if the person is not utilizing the information for his own benefit but rather shares or transfers the information to some another person it would still fall under insider trading.

Now the employees and officers of the company their family members or the close relatives also come within the meaning of insider trading. The price sensitive information is known to the employees or officers of the company, so there may be a situation where they do not trade on their own rather they will pass on the information to someone else and ask them to trade and share the profits with them.

Rationale

The Indian economy is identified as one of the fastest growing economies in the world and as it grows there is possibility of financial crimes happening. One such crime is insider trading.

An investor needs lots of disclosure of information so that he can take a decision whether he should make investment in securities of a company. The capital market to function efficiently one of the essential pre conditions is that all the market participants should have access to such information or the information should be equally available to all market participants at the same time. Now if the company insiders who are having access or possessing such information, which is sensitive information and this information is not available to the other market players or investors then this would lead to market distortion.

The rationale behind the prohibition of insider trading as quoted by Lord Lane in Attorney General's Reference No.1 of 1988 (1988) BCC 765 is ‘the obvious and understandable concern... about the damage to public confidence which insider dealing is likely to cause and the clear intention to prevent so far as possible what amounts to cheating when those with inside knowledge use that knowledge to make a profit in their dealing with others’.

Insider trading – Indian Regulatory Framework

The liberalization of India's economy in 1991 made a considerable development of capital market and regulatory reforms. The stock exchanges of a nation are the key segment of its capital market. To create a healthy capital market there is a need for proper regulation of the capital market. Any transactions based on confidential information of the company shall amount to insider trading as this information is unpublished price sensitive information which is not available in the public domain. This information can be used to avoid losses or to make some profits. It definitely amounts to a breach of fiduciary duties of Directors, the managers and officers of a company or connected persons as defined under the Securities Exchange Board of India (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 1992, towards the shareholders.

There is a need that the investor deals in the securities in a undisturbed manner and therefore it is needed that there should be a free and fair mechanism for transferring or trading of stocks in the secondary market. It demands the need that everyone gets convinced that no one gains from any information which is not in the public. This is the very purpose for enacting the insider trading laws and regulations. Every investor should trade in stocks on the basis of the information which is available in the public domain thereby creating a level playing field to all the investors. No one particularly the 'insiders' should deal with unpublished information'.

Controller of Capital Issues was set up in 1947 and was the main authority to ratify the issue of securities, and the amount, type and the price of securities. Later it was abolished and the Securities Exchange Board of India (SEBI) was set up in April 1988. On the recommendations of various Committees, SEBI formulated the SEBI (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations (1992).

In 2014, Indian market capitalization crossed some USD 1.6 trillion, making it world's ninth largest economy by market capitalization. SEBI has been constantly focussed on the development and regulation of the Indian capital market to improve the investors' confidence.

It was felt that there is a need to review and provide a more strong and efficient method in line with the global norms and standard to control insider trading in India. Thus, the new regulations i.e. SEBI (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulation, 2015 was introduced.

Provisions under the Companies Act, 2013

A company gets registered under the Companies Act. To trade its securities on the stock exchange the company has to list its securities on the stock exchange. The company to do so has to enter into the listing agreement with the stock exchange. On executing the listing agreement SEBI (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015 would be applicable.

The Companies Act, 2013 provides that 'No person including any director or key managerial personnel of a company shall enter into insider trading'. It further provides that in case there is any act in contravention there is civil as well as criminal liability.

Provisions under the SEBI Act, 1992

SEBI is the statutory body responsible for ensuring corporate governance in the securities market. The board needs to protect the interest of investors and promote the development of and regulate the securities market by such measures as it thinks appropriate. SEBI Act, 1992. prohibits Insider Trading.

Further, as per SEBI (Prohibition of Insider Trading) Regulations, 2015, no insider shall trade securities that are listed or proposed to be listed on a stock exchange when in possession of unpublished price sensitive information.

SEBI Act prescribes penalty for Insider Trading. Any person guilty of Insider Trading shall be liable to a penalty which shall not be less than ten lakh rupees but which may extend to twenty-five crore rupees or three times the amount of profits made out of insider trading, whichever is higher.

Insider trading Regulations – 2015

The new Insider Trading Regulations seem to be more optimistic, pragmatic and substantially in line with the global perspective to insider trading. It has improved the insider trading norms with clarity in the definitions and concepts of insider trading. The regulations also strengthen the definition of an 'insider'. Also the scope of 'connected persons' under the regulations has been widened to include persons related with the company in a contractual, fiduciary or employment association or having direct or indirect access to unpublished price-sensitive information.

The 2015 Regulations have clarified the definition of an insider; they have widened the meaning of a 'connected person', thereby expanding the scope of who constitutes an insider. This new regulations state that any person associated with the company by virtue of frequent communication in any capacity can be a connected person. Therefore a person can be said to be a connected person if his frequent communication with an insider leads to a reasonable inference of his possession of unpublished price sensitive information (UPSI), even in the absence of any direct evidence. Under the 2015 Regulations, the definition of UPSI has been expanded to bring within its ambit any information pertaining to the company which is not generally available including information pertaining to the financial results of the company, dividends, changes in capital structure, mergers and acquisitions as well as changes in key management personnel. The Regulations define 'generally available information' to include information that is accessible to the public on a non-discriminatory basis.

This new regulation is stricter in terms of punishment and a stronger legal enforcement framework in order to prevent insider trading. The regulation has given detailed definitions of an insider, unpublished price sensitive information, connected persons, trading, etc. which helps SEBI to make a better analysis while making a decision.

Judicial Perspective – Insider Trading:

There are few landmark cases in which opportunity was provided to judiciary for interpreting the provisions for Insider trading. In *Rakesh Agrawal vs SEBI*, the managing director (Rakesh Agrawal) of ABS Industries Ltd., entered into a contract with Bayer AG, a German business, which agreed to purchase more than 50% of ABS Industries Ltd.'s shares. Following UPSI's announcement of the acquisition, the accused sold a significant portion of his ABS Industries ownership, which he owned through his brother-in-law, Mr. I. P. Kedia. Considering Mr. Kedia to be a well-connected individual, SEBI held that Mr. Rakesh Agrawal was guilty of insider trading and directed him to deposit Rs. 34 lakhs with Investor Protection Funds of Stock Exchange, Mumbai and NSE (in equal proportion i.e. Rs.17 lakhs in each exchange) to pay any investor who may make a claim afterwards. On appeal to the Securities Appellate Tribunal (SAT), it was concluded that even if Mr. Agrawal had traded securities while in possession of UPSI, he was not guilty of insider trading because his actions were in the best interests of the company (as Bayer AG was not willing to acquire the company unless it could obtain a minimum of 51% of the shares) and there was no intention to make a profit. Further, SAT decided that in order to penalise an insider for violating the Regulations, it must be proven that the insider benefited unfairly from the trade. The tribunal also rejected SEBI's argument that insider trading jurisprudence is founded on the concept of 'disclose or abstain', and that an insider in possession of UPSI cannot trade in a company's stocks until he reveals the UPSI. The tribunal made it very clear that the intention or motive of the insider to be taken cognizance of though it is not specifically mentioned.

Also in *Hindustan Lever Limited vs. SEBI*, Hindustan Lever Ltd. ("HLL") bought 8 lakh shares of Brook Bond Lipton India Ltd. ("BBLIL") from Public Investment Institution, Unit Trust of India ("UTI") two weeks prior to the public announcement of the merger of two companies, i.e., HLL and BBLIL. SEBI, suspecting insider trading, issued a Show Cause Notice ("SCN") to the Chairman, all Executive Directors, the Company Secretary and the then Chairman of HLL. London-based Unilever was the parent company of HLL and BBLIL, and were operating under the same management. SEBI determined that HLL and its directors were insiders because they had prior knowledge of the merger. SEBI further determined that HLL was in the possession of UPSI as mentioned under Section 2(k) of the 1992 Regulations, which included any information regarding amalgamation/mergers/takeovers that "is not widely known or published by such company for general information, but which if published or known, is likely to substantially impact the price of securities of that company in the market". The issue before SAT was whether HLL was an insider and the information held by the HLL constituted UPSI. The SAT concurred with the SEBI order that the information accessible to HLL in regard to the merger went beyond self-generated information, i.e., information derived from the company's own decision-making. In addition, SAT stated that the presence of directors who were common to both HLL and BBLIL, as well as a common parent company in Unilever, indicated that they (i.e., HLL and BBLIL) were effectively managed together. As a result, HLL could be classified as an insider under the 1992 Regulations, and it was reasonable to assume that HLL was privy to the BBLIL board's decision-making on the merger issue. SAT observed that even in the merger of two healthy companies, there are synergistic possibilities that might

lead to price sensitivity for either company, on the subject of whether the information shared with HLL constituted UPSI. As a result, SAT concurred with SEBI's judgment that merger information was price sensitive (albeit not "unpublished").

Conclusion

Insider Trading in India is an offense according to Section 195 of the Companies Act, 2013 and Sections 12A, 15G of the Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992.

Insider trading would take place when any person who subscribes, buys or sells securities of a company on the basis of information which is non-public and price sensitive information. If any person deals or even agrees to deal or advises another person to do so shall be liable for insider trading. The insider regulations in India prohibit dealing, communicating or counselling on matters relating to insider trading. Violations of these prohibitions are considered as committing the offence of insider trading.

The regulatory bodies are tasked with responsibility and duties to prevent insider trading. It is very difficult or impossible for the regulatory authorities to come up with a full proof mechanism that can completely prevent insider trading. In spite of laws, rules regulations placed there is no mechanism that can completely prevent insider trading.

Now to control, limit or curb the threat of insider trading there lies a huge responsibility and duty on all the persons holding high positions in the company i.e directors, key managerial persons, officers and even some other persons of the company to preserve the price sensitive information. All these persons need to willingly initiate steps by setting high standards of ethical behaviour by not indulging into any activity that would amount to dealing on the basis of information that is not available in the public domain and is unpublished price sensitive information.